

A Study on Different Techniques of Laboratory Detection of Malaria in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Western India**Bhumika Baria¹, Amit Agravat², Gauravi Dhruva³, Krupal Pujara⁴**¹3rd year Resident, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India²Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India³Professor & Head, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College and Hospital, Rajkot, India

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Abstract:

Background: Malaria is one of the most prevalent parasitic infections in the world including India. It is a tropical, endemic protozoal infection. In most countries, its diagnosis is challenging. Microscopy is the gold standard method for its diagnosis in clinical practice as well as for research purpose. However, it is laborious, requiring significant skills and time, causing therapeutic delays. Rapid malaria diagnostic tests (RDTs) have made possible to obtain quick results from the blood examination. Various fast, reliable and easy to use RDTs are available which can detect Plasmodium falciparum and non-falciparum infections or both.

Objective: To study about different techniques for detection of malaria in a tertiary care hospital in Western India.

Materials and Methods: Study was conducted in the Central Clinical Laboratory (CCL), Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College, Rajkot, Gujarat, India over one year period between June 2023 to May 2024. Peripheral blood smear stained by Hematoxylin and Eosin Stain, Leishman stain and Field stain technique for conventional smear and thick smear preparation and commercially available rapid antigen detection kits were used for the diagnosis of malaria.

Results: During the 1-year period, rapid card test method showed 150 positives for malarial parasite. Of these, 127 cases were positive for *P. vivax* and 20 cases for *P. falciparum*. Peripheral blood smear method showed 139 cases positive for malarial parasite. Of these, 120 cases were positive for *P. vivax* and 17 cases for *P. falciparum* and 2 cases of co-infection. 24 cases were reported with thick smear preparation. 11 cases reported were peripheral blood smear negative. Among the cases, there were 46 females and 104 males. 20 – 29 years is the most affected age group which is followed by 30 – 39 years. Maximum samples were from the month of September with a positivity rate of 26 %.

Conclusion: RDTs based on detection of malaria antigen from whole blood are as specific as and more sensitive than microscopy (being considered as the gold standard method). However, peripheral blood smear method remains superior for accurate species differentiation, quantitation of parasite and maintenance of a permanent record. Other tests such as Flow cytometry, PCR, ELISA can be considered.

Keywords: Malaria, Microscopy, Rapid Diagnostic Tests.

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Introduction

Malaria is a protozoan infection caused by different Plasmodium species. Anopheles mosquitoes are the common vectors, seen in humid areas with temperatures between 20°C to 30°C. In the Indian subcontinent, Anopheles stephensi is the principle vector breeding in stagnant water [1]. The most serious type of malaria is caused by Plasmodium falciparum, which can also be fatal. The other human malaria species including *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale*, and sometimes *P. knowlesi* infection causes severe illness but is rarely fatal. [2] Symptoms such as fever, rigors, anemia,

enlargement of spleen, liver, etc. are reported. The total cases in India are 1.31 million (0.94 - 1.83 million) according to the WHO report estimates. [3] Various control programmes are being implemented due to which a 24% reduction had been recorded. West Bengal, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Odisha, Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Gujarat reported enormous decrease in cases from 14.3 million in 2010 to 5.7 million in 2018. For diagnosis of malaria, different diagnostic methods are being practiced such as peripheral blood smear examination, antigen demonstration

tests, serodiagnostics and molecular methods. Several advantages and disadvantages are reported for each technique used. From thick smear preparation, the density of parasitemia is expressed as percentage of erythrocytes parasitized or as the numbers of parasitized erythrocytes per microliter of blood.

Parasite load is assessed by using the plus system which is as follows: (1) Slight (+, 1–10 parasites/100 thick film fields), (2) Moderate (++ , 11–100 parasites/100 thick film fields), (3) High (+++, 1–10 parasites/ thick film field) and (4) Very high (++++, >10 parasites/ thick film field).

The gold standard method for the laboratory diagnosis of malarial parasite is microscopy. Alternatively, diagnostic method like RDTs is quick and easy which require little or no training. [4]. Histidine rich protein-2 (HRP-2) and Parasite lactate dehydrogenase (pLDH) are two malarial antigens suitable for rapid diagnosis. P. falciparum detection is based on the detection of histidine rich protein-2 and pLDH is used to detect P. vivax malaria.

RDTs use either monoclonal or polyclonal antibodies directed against the parasite antigen targets to detect the parasite antigens present in peripheral blood. RDTs can detect lactate dehydrogenase as well as histidine-rich protein 2.

Thus, antigen tests can differentially detect the causative species of Plasmodium whereas; antibody tests are unable to detect the causative species.

Materials and Methods

In the present study analysis of Malaria cases comprising total of 150 cases was carried out over a period of 1 year (between June 2023 to May 2024), in the Central Clinical Laboratory (CCL), Department of Pathology, PDU Medical College, Rajkot, Gujarat, India of indoor patients. Peripheral blood smear were stained with Feild stain technique for thick smear preparation and commercially available rapid antigen detection kits were used for the diagnosis.

Blood samples were collected in Ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid [EDTA] vials from the indoor patients. Thick smear preparation done using Feild stain, conventional smears prepared using Hematoxylin and eosin Stain & Leishman stain; and for rapid qualitative determination RDTs (based on detection of pLDH and histidine rich protein-2 Pf.HRP-2) were used. The patient’s name, age, sex were recorded.

Results

Among 150 total cases of malaria 100% (150) were positive by kit method and 92.67% (139) were positive by blood smear examination. (Table 1)

Table 1: Detection of Malaria Cases by Different Methods

Method	Positive For P. Vivax	Positive For P. Falciparum	Co- Infection
Microscopy (N=139 Cases)	120	17	2
Rapid Diagnostic Test(N=150 Cases)	127	20	3

Blood smear examination failed to detect 7 cases of P. vivax and 3 cases of P. falciparum and 1 case of co infection which were positive by Rapid card test, so total 11 cases were Peripheral blood film negative but rapid diagnostic test positive. There

was no case in which microscopy was positive and RDT negative. In this study total 150 samples were diagnosed to be malaria. In this 104(69.34%) were male and 46 (30.66%) were female participants, with male female ratio 2.26:1 (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Sex Wise Distribution of Malaria Cases

When ages of the participants was considered, 33(highest) were positive in 20-29 age group, followed by 29 positive in 30-39 age group and least 07 positive in 10-19 age group. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Distribution of Cases of Malaria in Various Age Groups

Most cases were seen in September i.e. 39 cases (26%) followed by August showing 26 cases (17.33%) and least cases were seen in February and March i.e. 2 cases (1.33%). (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Month Wise Distribution of Cases of Malaria

65% population affected by malaria was from rural areas. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Distribution of Malaria Cases in Rural and Urban Areas

24 cases were seen with high malarial parasite load showing positivity in thick smear preparation. (Table 2)

Table 2: Distribution of Malaria Cases According to Density of Malarial Parasite

Density Of Malarial Parasite	No. Of Parasites Seen On Thick Films	No. Of Cases
Slight (+)	1–10 parasites/100 thick film fields	8
Moderate (++)	11–100 parasites/100 thick film fields	7
High (+++)	1–10 parasites/thick film field	5
Very High (++++)	>10 parasites/ thick film field	4
Total No. Of Cases		24

Discussion

There should not be any delay in the diagnosis of malaria and it has to be considered as the health emergency. But its diagnosis is a significant challenge in the medical field [5, 6]. Smear microscopy is a commonly practiced technique for the diagnosis as well as for treatment monitoring and noting the drug resistance of malaria. In majority of the settings, peripheral blood smear is being used for the diagnosis of malaria, but requirement of prolonged time period and technical expertise are its major drawbacks. In spite of these drawbacks, low cost is the principle factor for considering smear microscopy for the diagnosis. Coleman RE et al., quoted that microscopy is the gold standard technique for the diagnosis of malaria [7]

The expectations behind the development of rapid malaria diagnostic technique was accuracy, rapidity and low price[8] .They also proved to be the backbone for the diagnosis especially in the areas where the microscopic facilities are not available [9,10]. There were 11 cases missed by the

peripheral smear microscopy. Among the missed cases, the cause was identified in 3 cases to be P.falciparum by the rapid diagnostic tests which could be due to sequestration of P. falciparum in the capillaries of the internal organs. [11]

When gender was considered, 69.34% (104) and 30.66% (46) cases were diagnosed as malaria positive respectively for male and female category. Abisha Jaya Singh et al. reported 80% and 20% cases respectively as males and females [12]. It was reported in the literature that more outdoor activity is the major cause for more positive results in the male group which exposes them to the bite of anopheles mosquito.

Age wise, malaria positivity was increased with the age in this study; which is also due to more outdoor activity. 20- 29 years was the most affected age group followed by 30 - 39 years age group. This correlates with S.R. Karlekar et al. [13] who reported 24.8 years as mean age group for malaria cases. Singh et al. [14] reported maximum cases in 21 - 30 years of age, Chourasia MK [15] in 24-48

years and Fazal Shan [16] in 31 – 40 years (Table 3).

Table 3: Various Studies Showing Distribution Of Malaria Cases In Different Age Groups.

Reference Study	Maximum Cases In The Age Group
Present Study (Rajkot, Gujarat, India, 2024)	20-29 years
Singh et al (Mumbai, Maharashtra, India 2015)	21-30 years
Chourasia MK (Chhattisgarh, India, 2014)	24- 48 years
S.R. Karlekar (Maharashtra, India, 2012)	40- 50 years
Fazal Shan(Dir lower, Pakistan, 2023)	31 – 40 years

Gujarat has plains, hilly areas, highland, deserts and coastline areas. It experiences seasons of hot dry summer season in April to mid-May, monsoon from mid-May to September, autumn from October to November, winter from December to January and spring from February to March.

Maximum temperature rises to around 49°C and the minimum temperature reaches upto 12° C. Relative humidity ranges between 34 and 78 %.

Malaria transmission occurs throughout the year but it peaks during the monsoon season. The high prevalence of malaria in this period could be due to collection of water after rainy season and breeding of mosquitoes in stagnant water which continues till December.

Similar findings were reported from Sanjeev Kumar [17], Pandey S, Singh A. [18] and K Abdullahi [19] (Table 4)

Table 4: Various Studies Showing Distribution Of Malaria Cases Month Wise.

Reference Study	Maximum Prevalence Of Malaria Seen (Month Wise)
Present Study (Rajkot, India, 2024)	September, August
Sanjeev Kumar (Rajasthan, India, 2015)	July, August
Pandey S, Singh A. (Chhattisgarh, India, 2009)	October
K Abdullahi (North Nigeria, Africa, 2009)	August
Fazal Shan(Dir lower, Pakistan, 2023)	September

65% population affected by malaria was from rural areas due to poor drainage system and stagnant collection of water favouring breeding of mosquitoes.

To reduce morbidity and mortality due to malaria, its detection and effective treatment is of utmost importance. Rapid diagnostic tests can only

supplement in absence of smear examination and Expert opinion. Peripheral blood smear study is simple, least expensive but time consuming thereby delaying diagnosis; whereas new techniques like antigen detection assays are rapid, simple and easy to interpret. However microscopy remains the gold standard as it provides more information.

Figure 5: Showing Ring Form of Plasmodium Vivax

Figure 6: Ring (Red Arrow) and Trophozoite (Blue Arrow) Form Of Plasmodium Vivax

Figure 7: Showing Schizont Form of Plasmodium Vivax

Figure 8: Showing Ring and Gametocyte Form of Plasmodium Falciparum

Conclusion

Malaria can be underdiagnosed using the conventional methods and any rapid technique should be complimentary and not counterproductive. RDTs are rapid, not requiring expertise are useful in routine diagnosis. Even so, peripheral blood smear examination still remains superior for accurate differentiation of malaria species, quantification of parasite load and for maintaining a permanent record. RDTs should be used only as complimentary method with microscopy to improve the diagnosis of malaria. However; other confirmatory tests such as Flow cytometry, PCR, ELISA can also be considered.

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